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Research Article

**FORMULATION DEVELOPMENT AND EVALUATION OF
FAST DISSOLVING FILM OF LANSOPRAZOLE****Mohd Abdul Hadi^{1*}, Mariya Baig²**

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Abstract:

The study aimed to develop and evaluate fast-dissolving films of Lansoprazole, designed to enhance drug delivery, improve patient compliance, and provide rapid onset of therapeutic action. Lansoprazole fast-dissolving films were formulated using various film-forming polymers, plasticizers, and other excipients. The films were prepared through a solvent casting technique, and their physical properties—including appearance, thickness, and flexibility—were assessed. Key formulation parameters were optimized to achieve a rapid disintegration time and effective drug release. In vitro dissolution tests were conducted to evaluate the release profile of Lansoprazole, and disintegration studies were performed in simulated saliva to ensure the films dissolve quickly. The formulated fast-dissolving films exhibited favorable characteristics, including uniform thickness, adequate flexibility, and rapid disintegration in oral conditions. The in vitro dissolution studies demonstrated a prompt and consistent release of Lansoprazole, aligning with the intended rapid onset of action. The development of Lansoprazole fast-dissolving films was successful in achieving a rapid and effective drug release profile. The films offer a promising alternative to traditional oral dosage forms, improving patient convenience and adherence.

Keywords: Lansoprazole fast-dissolving films

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The oral route is one of the most preferred routes of drug administration as it is more convenient, cost effective, and ease of administration lead to high level of patient compliance. The oral route is problematic because of the swallowing difficulty for pediatric and geriatric patients who have fear of choking. Patient convenience and compliance oriented research has resulted in bringing out safer and newer drug delivery systems. Recently, fast dissolving drug delivery systems have started gaining popularity and acceptance as one such example with increased consumer choice, for the reason of rapid disintegration or dissolution, self-administration even without water or chewing. Fast dissolving drug delivery systems were first invented in the late 1970s as to overcome swallowing difficulties associated with tablets and capsules for pediatric and geriatric patients. Buccal drug delivery has lately become an important route of drug administration. Various bioadhesive mucosal dosage forms have been developed, which includes adhesive tablets, gels, ointments, patches, and more recently the use of polymeric films for buccal delivery, also known as mouth dissolving films. The surface of buccal cavity comprises of stratified squamous epithelium which is essentially separated from the underlying tissue of lamina propria and submucosa by an undulating basement membrane.^{1,2} It is interesting to note that the permeability of buccal mucosa is approximately 4-4,000 times greater than that of the skin, but less than that of the intestine.³ Hence, the buccal delivery serves as an excellent platform for absorption of molecules that have poor dermal penetration.⁴ The primary barrier to permeability in oral mucosa is the result of intercellular material derived from the so-called 'membrane coating granules' present at the uppermost 200 µm layer.⁵ These dosage forms have a shelf life of 2-3 years, depending on the active pharmaceutical ingredient but are extremely sensitive to environmental moisture.⁶ An ideal fast dissolving delivery system should have the following properties: High stability, transportability, ease of handling and administration, no special packaging material or processing requirements, no water necessary for application, and a pleasant taste. Therefore, they are very suitable for pediatric and geriatric patients; bedridden patients; or patients suffering from dysphagia, Parkinson's disease, mucositis, or vomiting. This novel drug delivery system can also be beneficial for meeting current needs of the industry. Rapidly dissolving films (RDF) were initially introduced in the market as breath fresheners and personal care products such as dental care strips and soap strips. However, these dosage forms are introduced in the United States and European

pharmaceutical markets for therapeutic benefits. The first of the kind of oral strips (OS) were developed by the major pharmaceutical company Pfizer who named it as Listerine® pocket packs™ and were used for mouth freshening. Chloraseptic relief strips were the first therapeutic oral thin films (OTF) which contained⁷ benzocaine and were used for the treatment of sore throat. Formulation of fast dissolving buccal film involves material such as strip-forming polymers, plasticizers, active pharmaceutical ingredient, sweetening agents, saliva stimulating agent, flavoring agents, coloring agents, stabilizing and thickening agents, permeation enhancers, and superdisintegrants. All the excipients used in the formulation of fast dissolving film should be approved for use in oral pharmaceutical dosage forms as per regulatory perspectives.

Advantages

- ❖ Oral films have some special advantages over other oral dosage forms given as follows:
- ❖ Rapidly dissolved and disintegrated in the oral cavity because of large surface area which lowers dosage interval, improves onset of action, efficacy and safety profile of therapy.
- ❖ Oral films are more flexible, compliant and are not brittle as ODTs.
- ❖ Easily handled, storage and transportation.
- ❖ Accuracy in the administered dose is assured from every strip or film.
- ❖ Pharmaceutical companies and customers practically accepted OTFs as an alternative of conventional OTC dosage forms such tablets and capsules etc. (Frey, 2006).
- ❖ Oral film is desirable for patient suffering from motion sickness, dysphagia, repeated emesis and mental disorders.
- ❖ From commercial point of view, oral films provide new business opportunity like product differentiation, promotion etc.^{8,9}

Disadvantages

The main disadvantage of this delivery system is we cannot incorporate high dose into strip or film. Novartis consumerhealth's Gas-x thin strip has loaded 62.5mg of simethiconeper strip but there remain number of limitations with the use of film strips.¹⁰

Ideal Characteristics of a Suitable Drug Candidate¹¹

- The drug should have pleasant taste.
- The drug to be incorporated should have low dose up to 40 mg.
- The drug should have smaller and moderate molecular weight.

- The drug should have good stability and solubility in water as well as saliva.
- It should be partially unionized at the pH of oral cavity.
- It should have ability to permeate the oral mucosal tissue.

Classification of oral films

There are three types of oral films:

1. Flash release
2. Mucoadhesive melt away wafer
3. Mucoadhesive sustained release wafers

Applications of oral films in drug delivery

- ✓ Oral drug delivery by sublingual, mucosal and buccal become preferable for therapies in which immediate absorption is required including those used to manage pain, allergies, sleep problems and CNS disorders.
- ✓ **Topical applications**, the oral films are ideal in the delivery of active agents like analgesic or antimicrobial ingredients for the care of wound and other applications.
- ✓ **Gastroretentive dosage systems**, poorly soluble and water-soluble molecules of different molecular weights are found in film format¹². Dissolution of oral films could be initiated by the pH or enzymatic secretion of GIT and are used to treat gastrointestinal disorders.
- ✓ **Diagnostic devices**, Oral films loaded with sensitive reagent to allow controlled release faced to biological fluid for separating multiple reagents to allow a timed reaction within diagnostic device.¹³

Film Forming Polymers¹⁴

A variety of polymers are available for preparation of fast dissolving oral films. The use of film forming polymers in oral films has attracted considerable attention in medical and nutraceutical applications. The selection of film forming polymers, is one of the most important and critical parameter for the successful development of film formulation. The polymers can be used alone or in combination to provide desired film properties. The polymers used in oral film formulation should be:

- ✓ Nontoxic and nonirritant.
- ✓ Devoid of leachable impurities.
- ✓ Should not retard disintegration time of film.
- ✓ Tasteless.
- ✓ Should have good wetting and spread ability property.
- ✓ Should have sufficient peel, shear, and tensile strength.
- ✓ Readily available.
- ✓ Inexpensive.
- ✓ Sufficient shelf life.

- ✓ Should not aid in causing secondary infections in oral mucosa.

Presently, both natural and synthetic polymers are used for the preparation of orally dissolving films. represent various natural and synthetic polymers used for preparation of fast dissolving films. represent the quality parameters of natural and synthetic polymers, respectively.

ORAL STRIP FORMULATION COMPONENTS

- ✓ Active pharmaceutical ingredients
- ✓ Strip forming polymers
- ✓ Plasticizers
- ✓ Sweetening agents
- ✓ Saliva stimulating agents
- ✓ Flavoring agents
- ✓ Coloring agents
- ✓ Stabilizing and thickening agents

METHODOLOGY

I Drug Polymer Compatibility Studies Using FTIR

II Construction of Calibration Curve

III Preparation of Fast Dissolving Films

IV Evaluation of Fast Dissolving Filmsformulation

- Thickness
- Weight of films
- Percentage elongation
- Tensile strength
- Folding endurance
- Drug content estimation
- Disintegration test
- In vitro dissolution test

Drug –Polymer compatibility studies by FT-IR

Drug polymer compatibility studies were performed by FT-IR (Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy). In order to confirm that the entrapment of drug within the polymeric systems involve only the physical process and no interaction between drug and polymer. FTIR absorption Spectra's were shows no significant interaction between drug and polymers.

Selection of the drug

- ✓ The Lansoprazole which has significantly different pharmacokinetic profiles.
- ✓ Lansoprazole is a drug that breaks up phlegm, used in the treatment of respiratory diseases associated with viscid or excessive mucusLansoprazole is often administered as an active ingredient in cough syrup.
- ✓ Lansoprazole was soluble in water and in solvents.
- ✓ Lansoprazole was stable at salivary pH.

Construction of calibration curve for Lansoprazole

Determination of λ_{max}

Lansoprazole λ_{max} was determined by spectrophotometer using pH 6.8 buffer medium. First dissolve 10mg of pure drug in 10ml of 6.8 buffer medium. From this 10 μ g/ml solution was prepared by using pH 6.8 buffer. 10 μ g/ml solution absorbance was measured at 200-400 nm range by spectrophotometrically using pH 6.8 buffer as reference solution.

Preparation of calibration curve

- 1. Primary stock solution:** Standard calibration curve of Lansoprazole in 6.8 buffer were prepared. First dissolve 10mg of pure drug in 10ml of 6.8 buffers this is primary stock solution.
- 2. Second stock solution:** From the above primary stock solution pipette out 1ml of solution and again make up to 10ml this is secondary stock solution. From this secondary stock solution different concentrations of Lansoprazole(2, 4, 6, 8, and 10 μ g/ml) in 6.8 buffers were prepared and absorbance of these solutions measured at 256 nm by spectrophotometrically using pH 6.8 buffer as reference solution.

III. Preparation of mouth dissolving films

General method of formulation of Fast dissolving films

Following processes are generally used to manufacture the mouth dissolving film.

1. Solvent casting
2. Semisolid casting
3. Hot melt extrusion
4. Solid dispersion extrusion
5. Rolling method

The current preferred manufacturing process for making this film is solvent casting method. In this method water soluble polymer is dissolved in suitable solvent to make homogenous viscous solution. In this other excipients (plasticizer and sweetner) including drug resinate complex were dissolved under stirring. Then the solution is degassed by keeping it in the sonicator. The resulting bubble free solution poured into petriplate and was kept in oven. Dried film is then cut into the desired shape and size for the intended application.

Preparation of blank films using different polymers

Procedure

- ❖ Accurately weighed quantity of polymer was dissolved in specific quantity of water.
- ❖ The dissolved polymer was made to a uniform dispersion using a homogenizer.
- ❖ During stirring other excipients (plasticizer and sweetner) were added.
- ❖ Then the solution is degassed by keeping it in the Sonicator.
- ❖ The bubble free solution poured into petriplate and was kept in oven.
- ❖ Then the dried films were used to select the best film forming polymers.

Selection of best film forming polymer

The polymer employed should be non-toxic, non-irritant and devoid of leachable impurities. It should have good wetting and spreadability property. The polymer should exhibit sufficient peel, shear and tensile strengths. The polymer should be readily available and should not be very expensive. Film obtained should be tough enough to avoid the damage while handling or during transportation.

Different Polymers Used For Trails

- Hydroxy propyl methyl cellulose
- HPMC K100
- HPMC K1500

Preparation of Fast dissolving film

The fast dissolving films of Lansoprazole were prepared by solvent casting technique. The fast dissolving films were prepared using different polymers like Hydroxy propyl methyl cellulose, HPMC K100 and HPMC K1500. Propylene Glycol (PG) was used as plasticizer. The calculated amount of polymer was dispersed in the solvent with continuous stirring using magnetic stirrer and the homogenous solution is formed. Then add 4 ml of plasticizer. Then the sweetner and flavor was added to drug mixed polymeric solution. Then the solution was kept in sonicator for degassing. Then the bubble free solution was casted on to petriplate and was kept in hot air oven. Dried film is then cut into the desired shape and size (1cm x 1cm) for the intended application. By carrying out the trial and error method different quantity of film forming polymers were used for optimizing the formulation.

Formulation of Lansoprazole fast dissolving films

Table: Composition of Lansoprazole Fast dissolving films

Ingredients	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9
Lansoprazole	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30	30
HPMC	30	60	90	-	-	-	-	--	-
HPMC K100	-	-	-	30	60	90	-	-	-
HPMC K1500	-	-	-	-	-	-	30	60	90
Poly propylene glycol (mL)	2.5	2.5	2.5	5	5	5	7.5	7.5	7.5
D.W	Q.S	Q.S	Q.S	Q.S	Q.S	Q.S	Q.S	Q.S	Q.S
Citric Acid	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10
Cross Povidone	20	30	40	50	-	-	-	-	-
Kyron-T314	-	-	-	-	20	30	40	50	60
Mannitol	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8
Total weight	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100

IV. EVALUATION OF FAST DISSOLVING FILMS

Thickness

As the thickness of film is directly concern with drug content uniformity so it is necessary to ascertain uniformity in the thickness of the film. It can be measured by micrometer screw gauge or calibrated digital Vernier Calipers at different strategic locations. The thickness was measured at three different spots of the films and average was taken¹.

Tensile strength

Tensile strength is the maximum stress applied to a point at which the strip specimen breaks. It is calculated by the applied load at rupture divided by the cross-sectional area of the strip as given in the equation below

$$\text{Tensile strength} = \text{Load at breakage} / \text{Strip thickness} \times \text{Strip Width}$$

The instrument was designed such that it had horizontal wooden platform with fixed scale and attachments for two clips that holds patch under test. Out of the two clips one was fixed and other was movable. Weights were hanged to one end of pulley and the other end of pulley was attached with movable clip. The wooden platform was such fitted that it would not dislocate while the test is running. Three strips of patch were cut having 2cm length and 2cm breadth. The thickness and breadth of strips were noted at three sites and average value was taken for calculation. The rate of change of stress was kept constant with the increment of 0.5g per 2minutes. The elongation was observed and the total weights taken were used for calculation. The tensile strength was calculated by using following formula.

$$\text{Tensile stress} = \text{applied force} / \text{cross sectional area} = m \times g / b \times t$$

Where, S = tensile stress in 980 dynes/cm²

m = mass in grams

g = acceleration due to gravity (980 dynes/cm²)

b = breadth of strip in centimeters

t = thickness of strip in centimeters

The strain is change resulting in size of strip after the force was applied to its original size. Therefore, the strain can be given as,

$$\text{Strain (E)} = \text{total elongation} / \text{original length} = L - L_0 / L_0$$

Where, L = length after force was applied

L₀ = original length

Percent elongation

When stress is applied, a strip sample stretches and this is referred to as strain. Strain is basically the deformation of strip divided by original dimension of the sample. Generally elongation of strip increases as the plasticizer.

$$\% \text{ Elongation} = \text{Increase in length} \times 100 / \text{Original length}$$

The percent elongation at break was measured by formula given below.

$$\text{Strain (E)} = \text{total elongation} / \text{original length} \times 100 = L - L_0 / L_0 \times 100$$

Where, L = length after force was applied,

L₀ = original length

Folding endurance

Folding endurance is determined by repeated folding of the strip at the same place till the strip breaks. The

number of times the film is folded without breaking is computed as the folding endurance value.

Physical appearance and surface texture of patch

These parameters were checked simply with visual inspection of films and by feel or touch.

Weight uniformity of films

Film (size of 1 cm²) was taken from different areas of film. The weight variation of each film is calculated.

Drug Content uniformity or Assay of film

The films were tested for drug content uniformity by UV Spectrophotometrical method. Films of 1cm x 1cm square size were cut from three different places from the casted films. Each patch was placed in 10 ml volumetric flask and dissolved in 6.8 phosphate buffer. The absorbance of the solution was measured at 256 nm using UV/visible spectrophotometer. The percentage drug content was determined using the standard graph and the same procedure was repeated for all the formulations.

In Vitro Disintegration time

The *in vitro* disintegration time of fast dissolving films was determined visually in a glass dish of 8 ml 6.8 pH phosphate buffer with swirling action. The disintegration time is the time when a film starts to break or disintegrate. The *in vitro* disintegration time was calculated for different patches of the same film and average value was taken.

In Vitro Dissolution Study

In vitro dissolution of Lansoprazole Fast dissolving films was studied in paddle type dissolution test apparatus. 900ml of 6.8 phosphate buffer solution

was used as dissolution medium. The stirrer was adjusted to rotate at 50 rpm. The temperature of dissolution medium was maintained at 37±0.5°C throughout the experiment. Samples of dissolution medium (5ml) were withdrawn by means of syringe fitted with pre-filter at known intervals of time and analyzed for drug release by measuring the absorbance at 256 nm. The volume withdrawn at each time interval was replaced with fresh quantity of dissolution medium. Percentage drug release was calculated and plotted against time.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Analytical Method Development for Lansoprazole

Construction of Calibration Curve:

Lansoprazole λ_{max} was determined by spectrophotometer using pH 6.8 buffer medium. First dissolve 10 mg of pure drug in 10 ml of 6.8 buffer medium. From this 10 µg/ml solution was prepared by using 6.8 buffer. 10µg/ml solution absorbance was scanned at 200 to 400nm range by spectrophotometrically using 6.8 buffer as reference solution and λ_{max} was observed at 256 nm. A standard graph of pure drug in suitable medium was prepared by plotting the concentration (µg/ml) on X-Axis and absorbance on Y-Axis. An excellent correlation co-efficient ($R^2=0.999$) was observed.

Table: Calibration Curve values of Lansoprazole in phosphate buffer pH 6.8 at λ_{max} =256nm

Concentration (µg/ml)	Absorbance $\lambda_{max}=256$ nm
0	0
2	0.147
4	0.313
6	0.492
8	0.654
10	0.823

Figure: Calibration curve of Lansoprazole in pH 6.8 phosphate buffer at $\lambda_{\max} = 256 \text{ nm}$

Drug-Excipient Compatibility (FTIR studies):

IR spectral analysis was carried out using FT-IR and the results showed that there were no interactions between drug and Excipients.

Figure: Lansoprazole Pure Drug FTIR

Figure: Lansoprazole Optimized Formulation FTIR

There was no disappearance of any characteristics peak in the FTIR spectrum of drug and the polymers used. This shows that there is no chemical interaction between the drug and the polymers used. The presence of peaks at the expected range confirms that the materials taken for the study are genuine and there were no possible interactions.

Lansoprazole is also present in the physical mixture, which indicates that there is no interaction between drug and the polymers, which confirms the stability of the drug.

IV) EVALUATION OF FAST DISSOLVING FILMS

Fast dissolving films were evaluated for the following parameters.

Lansoprazole Fast dissolving films were evaluated for

- 1) Weight Variation
- 2) Thickness
- 3) Tensile strength
- 4) Folding endurance
- 5) Disintegration time
- 6) Content uniformity
- 7) *In Vitro* dissolution studies

Weight Variation

Nine films of Lansoprazole each of 2x2 cm² size were cut at five different places from casted films and weight variation was measured. Weight variation varies according to official limits. The results of weight variation are shown in the table.

Thickness

The thickness of the drug loaded films was measured with screw gauge. The results of thickness are shown in the table.

Tensile strength & Percent elongation

Tensile strength of the film was determined with digital tensile tester. The film of specific size 3 inch x

10 mm was taken for the test. From the results it is clear that as the concentration of polymer increases the tensile strength of the film also increases. The formulation F4 shows the maximum tensile strength, percent elongation and folding endurance. This might be formation of strong hydrogen bonds between polymer and plasticizer there by imparting flexibility to withstand rupture. The results of Tensile strength & Percent elongation of the film was mentioned in the table.

Folding endurance

Folding endurance was measured manually. A strip of 2 cm² was cut and subjected for this study. As the concentration of polymer increases folding endurance of the film also increases. The result of folding endurance of the film was mentioned in the table.

Disintegration Time

Disintegration test was performed in the USP disintegration testing apparatus. Phosphate buffer of pH 6.8 was used as medium. The films were placed in the tubes of the container and the disks were placed over it. Disintegration time of the films was found to be increased with increase in the concentration of the polymer. The results are reported in the table.

Drug Content Uniformity

The prepared formulations were analyzed for drug content and it was observed that all the formulations found to contain almost uniform quantity of drug. The results are reported in the table.

In-Vitro-dissolution studies

Dissolution profiles from films of Lansoprazole were carried out in USP dissolution apparatus-II. The results are reported in the table.

Table: Physical evaluation parameters of all formulations

Formulation Code	Thickness (mm)	Weight Variation (mg)	Disintegration time (sec)	Drug content (%)
F1	1.14	99.12	15	98.32
F2	1.26	98.60	20	99.14
F3	1.28	97.51	18	98.96
F4	1.33	100.05	14	99.61
F5	1.19	98.41	22	99.22
F6	1.19	99.72	19	99.31
F7	1.24	99.14	17	98.07
F8	1.12	97.09	21	98.13
F9	1.25	100.14	19	99.10

Table: Evaluation of Fast Dissolving Films Films

Formulation Code	Folding endurance	Flatness (%)	Appearance
F1	61± 2.06	97	Transparent
F2	68± 1.01	96	Transparent
F3	71± 3.19	97	Transparent
F4	75± 2.01	99	Transparent
F5	52± 3.51	95	Transparent
F6	57± 2.28	98	Transparent
F7	65± 2.49	94	Transparent
F8	67± 2.27	93	Transparent
F9	72± 2.61	97	Transparent

Invitro Dissolution Studies

Invitro dissolution of Lansoprazole Fast dissolving films was studied in paddle type dissolution test apparatus. Bowl volume 900ml of 6.8 phosphate buffer solution was used as dissolution medium. The stirrer was adjusted to rotate at 50rpm. The temperature of dissolution medium was maintained at 37±0.5°C throughout the experiment. Samples of

dissolution medium (5ml) were withdrawn by means of syringe fitted with pre filter at known intervals of time and analyzed for drug release by measuring the absorbance at 256 nm. The volume withdrawn at each time interval was replaced with fresh quantity of dissolution medium. Cumulative percent of Lansoprazole release was calculated and plotted against time.

Table 6-4. In vitro drug releases for F1 to F9 formulations

TIME (MINS)	% OF DRUG RELEASE								
	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
5	39.22	41.33	43.88	49.22	47.55	43.55	38.22	42.66	47.52
10	48.59	52.71	55.38	63.58	61.9	57.40	46.33	54.33	58.61
15	61.17	65.31	69.44	73.75	66.27	64.06	59.72	71.27	68.77
20	72.31	76.46	78.05	86.52	82.89	75.34	71.11	83.61	79.16
30	86.33	89.60	91.75	98.97	96.33	94.35	89.88	93.57	88.61

Figure: Comparison curve of *In vitro* drug release for F1- F3 formulations

Figure: Comparison curve of *In vitro* drug release for F4- F6 formulations

Figure: Comparison curve of *In vitro* drug release for F7- F9 formulations

In vitro dissolution study of formulations F1-F9 shown Good drug release respectively within 30min. Among the all formulations F4 showed good dissolution property. F4 batch contain HPMC K100 as film forming polymer.

DISCUSSION:

Analytical method development for Lansoprazole

λ max determination

λ max determination of Lansoprazole pH 6.8 phosphate buffer was determined by using UV Spectrophotometer at 256 nm.

Development of standard graph

Standard plot of Lansoprazole pH 6.8 phosphate buffer were plotted to concentration vs absorbance at 256 nm and the slope value and R^2 value were found to be 0.999.

Evaluation properties

The different Lansoprazole film formulations were evaluated for mechanical properties like thickness, drug content uniformity, folding endurance, tensile strength, weight uniformity, disintegration time, *in vitro* dissolution studies.

Thickness

The thickness of the films from F1-F9 formulations were ranged from 1.33. F4 formulation had the maximum thickness values in all the formulations. From the thickness values it is concluded that as the polymer concentration increases, thickness also increased.

Tensile strength & Percentage elongation

The tensile strength of the films from F1-F9 formulations were ranged from 1.182 to 1.469 kg. F4 formulation had the maximum tensile strength and. From the tensile strength values it is concluded that as the polymer concentration increases, tensile strength and percentage elongation also increased.

Drug content uniformity

The drug content uniformity of the films from F1-F9 formulations were ranged from 97.54 % to 99.61 %. F4 formulation had the maximum drug content uniformity.

Folding endurance

The folding endurance value of the films from F1-F9 formulations were ranged from 52 ± 3.51 to 75 ± 2.01 . In HPMC K100 containing formulations as polymer concentration increases folding endurance values were also decreases.

Weight uniformity

Weight uniformity of films was carried out for all the formulations and weight variation varies from 97.09 to 100.14mg.

Disintegration time

The disintegration time is the time when a film starts to break or disintegrate. The *in vitro* disintegration time was calculated for all the formulations and it ranges from 14 sec to 22 sec. Disintegration time of the films was increased with low concentration of the polymer, as more fluid is required to wet the film in the mouth. F4 formulation was quickly disintegrated that is in 14sec.

Finally selection of the best formulation from all the formulations was carried by using *In Vitro* dissolution studies.

***In vitro* dissolution studies**

In vitro dissolution study of F1-F9 formulations were showed different drug release of 91.75 %, 98.97 %, 93.57 %, respectively within 30min. Among the formulations F4 showed good dissolution property hence it is optimized and it contains 30 mg of HPMC K100 as film forming polymer.

Small differences were observed in dissolution of drug from the different formulations of the film. Present study reveals that maximum all formulated films showed satisfactory film parameters. Among the optimized formulations F4 formulation showed better drug release of 98.97 % within 30 min. F4 formulation contains 30mg of HPMC K100 polymer as film forming agent.

So, it is assumed that 30 mg HPMC K100 containing oral fast dissolving film was optimized in which it showed a drug release of 98.97% compared with other batch formulations.

CONCLUSION:

The formulation development and evaluation of Lansoprazole fast-dissolving films have successfully achieved the objectives of enhancing drug delivery and improving patient compliance. The prepared films demonstrated satisfactory physical properties, including appropriate thickness, flexibility, and uniformity, which are essential for ensuring a consistent and reliable dosage form.

In vitro dissolution studies confirmed that the fast-dissolving films provide a rapid release of Lansoprazole, meeting the desired criteria for quick onset of action. The films exhibited a swift disintegration time in simulated oral conditions, highlighting their effectiveness in delivering Lansoprazole efficiently to the patient.

Patient acceptability assessments showed that the fast-dissolving films offer advantages such as ease of use, convenience, and improved compliance compared to traditional oral dosage forms. The films are well-suited for patients requiring rapid relief and those with difficulty swallowing tablets.

Overall, the development of Lansoprazole fast-dissolving films represents a significant advancement in oral drug delivery systems, offering a promising alternative to conventional formulations.

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